

A study on the assessment criteria of seafarers' non-technical skills

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17036854>

Received 18 April 2025

Accepted for publication 11 June 2025

Published 09 September 2025

Abstract

As the technical skills of employees are replaced by digitalization, machines, and autonomous systems with the developing technology, non-technical skills of employees have come to the forefront. In this context, it is very important to improve the non-technical skills of seafarers working in maritime transportation. In this study, international training and assessment standards, especially STCW (Standards of Training, Certification, and Watchkeeping for Seafarers), industrial practices, and academic studies on non-technical skills of seafarers have been examined in detail through a comprehensive literature review, and non-technical competence criteria of seafarers have been put forward. Teamwork, communication, situational awareness, decision making, leadership, and managerial skills were identified as the five main criteria for the evaluation of seafarers' non-technical skills, and sub-criteria were listed under each main criterion. The aim of the study is to create a systematic list of criteria to be used in the assessment of seafarers' non-technical skills. The outputs of the study can be used in the crew recruitment management process of maritime companies and maritime training institutions. The study concludes with the identification of five key non-technical skill areas, each supported by defined sub-criteria, providing a practical reference framework for assessment purposes.

Keywords: non-technical skills, maritime training, competency assessment, seafarer, STCW

1. Introduction

Non-technical skills refer to a set of interpersonal abilities that encompass communication, leadership, teamwork, decision-making, and situational awareness. These skills are distinct from the technical

competencies necessary for performing specific tasks, such as operating machinery or executing particular procedures. Nevertheless, non-technical skills enhance the application of technical skills, thereby increasing overall efficiency and effectiveness. The significance of Non-Technical Skills lies in their capacity to improve safety and productivity in the workplace (Flin, R. et al., 2003; CAA, 2006).

The STCW convention establishes competency standards for seafarers. Adopted by the IMO, the convention outlines essential requirements for the training, certification, and watchkeeping of seafarers, aimed at enhancing safety at sea, which encompasses the protection of life, property, and the marine environment. The STCW encompasses several key components, including basic safety training (such as firefighting, first aid, and personal survival techniques), specialized training tailored to various ranks and roles (including deck officers and engine room staff), and regular updates and revalidation of certifications. Within the framework of the STCW, behavioural skills pertain to the interpersonal and communication competencies necessary for seafarers to function effectively in their positions, thereby promoting safety and collaboration on board vessels (Allen, 2022; IMO, 2017).

Although the STCW primarily emphasizes technical skills, safety protocols, and operational expertise, behavioural skills are equally vital for fostering a cohesive and safe working atmosphere (IMO, 2017; ITF, 2010). The safe execution of operations and the prevention of incidents are fundamentally dependent on human competency, which encompasses both technical (hard) skills and non-technical (soft) skills. Historically, the primary emphasis within the industry has been on the development and evaluation of technical skills. Since 2010 (Manila Amendments), the STCW Convention has also acknowledged the importance of soft skill competencies, including leadership, managerial abilities, decision-making, teamwork, and communication. The tanker sector has recognized the necessity of placing greater emphasis on soft skills. The behaviour and attitudes of crew are critical components of a robust safety culture, fostering a safe working environment and contributing to the reduction of incidents (INTERTANKO and OCIMF, 2018). A competency-based approach serves as the most suitable theoretical framework for evaluating non-technical skills. This approach emphasizes the importance of developing and demonstrating an individual's competence in executing safety-critical tasks. The assessment of non-technical skills is fundamentally supported by behavioural marker systems, which are applicable across a wide range of high-risk work settings (Thomas, 2018).

In this study, firstly, non-technical skills that come to the forefront in the digital age are defined, and non-technical skills within the scope of seafarer qualifications are examined under five main headings through a literature review. In addition to academic studies on the subject, international regulations and industrial practices were found in the literature. The studies utilized in the creation of the systematic criteria list presented as a result of the study are included in the literature review section. Afterwards, a systematic list including details of assessment criteria for seafarers' non-technical skills is presented. Although there are studies in the literature similar to this study in which technical and non-technical skills of seafarers are examined and evaluation criteria are presented, the lack of a systematic list presented as a result of the current study is considered a gap in the literature. The limitation of this review is that only the criteria to be used in the evaluation of non-technical skills were examined, rather than the content and quality of non-technical skills, and therefore, a sufficient number of studies available in the literature were not reviewed and included in this study. Despite the limitations and shortcomings of the study, the resulting seafarers' non-technical competency assessment list provides a practical assessment tool for the maritime industry.

Although traditionally overlooked, non-technical skills have become central to ensuring safety and performance at sea. To address this, the present study systematically reviewed a range of sources,

including international conventions, industrial competency models, and academic studies, to identify core non-technical skill areas relevant to modern seafaring. To conduct this review, a structured search of academic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, was used. Keywords such as 'non-technical skills', 'seafarers', 'maritime training', and 'competency assessment' were used. In addition to academic studies, relevant documents from the IMO, STCW Convention, and maritime industry reports were also examined to ensure a comprehensive understanding of training standards and practices. This methodological approach allowed for a comprehensive mapping of competencies.

2. Literature Review

Non-technical skills, including leadership, teamwork, communication, situational awareness, decision-making, leadership and managerial skills, play a vital role in maritime operations, contributing significantly to both safety and efficiency. The assessment of seafarers' non-technical skills is increasingly recognized as essential for maritime safety and operational efficiency. Literature has explored various aspects of these skills, their importance, and methods for their assessment.

Barnett et al. (2006) highlight the significance of Non-Technical Skills (NTS) in maritime operations through an examination of recent accident reports and case studies. It explores advancements in simulator-based training designed to enhance competencies such as resource management, communication, and leadership among professionals in the maritime sector.

Fjeld et al. (2018) examine existing research on non-technical skills utilized by ship bridge officers. It emphasizes the importance of skills like situational awareness, decision-making, and teamwork in preventing maritime accidents. The study highlights the need for structured training programs to enhance these competencies among bridge officers. Another research of Fjeld and Tvat (2020) investigates the perceptions of bridge officers regarding non-technical skills in the context of bridge resource management training. The findings indicate that while participants acknowledge the significance of non-technical skills, there is a need for training programs to provide clearer definitions and instruction on these skills to enhance comprehension and practical application.

The effectiveness of the STCW convention in relation to both technical and non-technical competencies is researched in a study. It recommends that although technical skills are adequately addressed, there is a pressing requirement for enhanced focus on non-technical skills within training and evaluation frameworks (Sharma and Kim, 2021). Colzi et al. (2019) examine the soft skills that seafarers possess, underscoring their importance in conjunction with technical abilities. It stresses the necessity for holistic training initiatives that combine both hard and soft skills to improve overall effectiveness in maritime logistics. A modified Delphi method alongside the Best Worst Method (BWM) is utilized to ascertain the essential skills for contemporary seafarers in a study. It highlights communication as the paramount soft skill, indicating that training programs should prioritize the development of communication skills to meet contemporary maritime demands (Chowdhury, 2023).

Maria and Bournata (2021) conducted an empirical investigation into the influence of four specific soft skills: adaptability, communication, problem-solving, and teamwork, on the contextual performance of seafarers. They utilized an empirical survey method, employing a self-assessment questionnaire distributed among managers and employees within Greek shipping companies. The results demonstrated that these interpersonal skills have a beneficial impact on performance, underscoring the significance of cultivating such abilities among professionals in the maritime sector.

The prospective landscape of maritime education and training is examined, emphasizing the necessity for a holistic program that combines both technical and interpersonal skills in an article. The article

suggests the establishment of a knowledge triangle that includes academic institutions, industry stakeholders, and regulatory bodies, aimed at cultivating well-prepared maritime professionals capable of addressing the complexities of the 21st century (Agua et al., 2020)

The existing literature highlights the significant role of non-technical skills within the maritime sector. To improve safety and operational effectiveness, it is vital to incorporate the development of non-technical skills into maritime education and training initiatives, thereby equipping seafarers to effectively address the changing requirements of the industry.

3. Assessment Criteria

As a result of the literature review, teamwork, communication, situational awareness, decision making, leadership, and managerial skills were identified as the five main criteria for the evaluation of seafarers' non-technical skills, and sub-criteria were identified under each main criterion (Allen, 2022; Chauvin et al., 2013; Fjeld et al., 2020; Flin et al., 2003; IMO, 2017; Saeed et al., 2017; Thomas, 2018; Zheliaskov et al., 2024). The five main non-technical competence criteria and their interaction with each other are shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1. Five main criteria of seafarers' non-technical skills

3.1 Teamwork

Teamwork is a requirement to work effectively and cooperatively with others to achieve shared goals. It involves communication, collaboration, adaptability, and mutual respect among team members. This skill is very important in every profession, as most tasks today require collaboration rather than isolated work. Good teamwork helps improve productivity, encourages innovation, and strengthens workplace relationships (Laker and Powel, 2011; Robles, 2012). The sub-criteria of teamwork skill are listed below with their definitions.

- **Collaboration:** Team members engage in cooperative efforts, capitalizing on the strengths of one another and extending support to collectively attain shared objectives.
- **Information Share:** Members of the team are encouraged to engage in transparent and effective communication, disseminating ideas, expressing concerns, and providing feedback in a manner that is respectful and considerate.
- **Problem-Solving:** Collaborative efforts among team members are essential for the effective identification and resolution of problems, whereby each individual contributes their unique insights and areas of expertise.
- **Flexibility:** Team members are expected to exhibit adaptability, demonstrating a willingness to modify their approaches in response to evolving requirements or unforeseen obstacles.

- **Positive Attitude:** An optimistic and solution-oriented mindset is crucial for teams to effectively navigate challenges and sustain motivation, particularly during periods of adversity.
- **Conflict Resolution:** The occurrence of conflict within teams is an inherent aspect of group dynamics, necessitating management through constructive means. It is imperative for teams to develop strategies that facilitate respectful and productive resolution of disagreements.
- **Trust:** It is essential for team members to cultivate a sense of trust amongst themselves, ensuring that they fulfil their respective responsibilities and offer mutual support. Such trust is fostered through a consistent demonstration of reliability and integrity.
- **Accountability:** Each individual must assume responsibility for their designated tasks and actions. Team members are encouraged to foster a culture of accountability towards one another in a manner that is constructive.

3.2 Communication

The ability to express ideas clearly and understand others effectively through speaking, writing, and listening can be defined as communication skill. It plays a key role in building relationships, solving problems, and working as part of a team. Strong communication skills help ensure clarity, reduce conflict, and improve productivity (Andrews and Higson, 2008). The sub-criteria of communication skill are listed below with their definitions.

- **Body Language:** Non-verbal cues play a significant role in communication. This encompasses facial expressions, gestures, posture, and eye contact. Affirmative body language can enhance the conveyed message, whereas negative body language may lead to misunderstandings.
- **Tone:** The manner in which a message is delivered can be as significant as the content itself. A respectful, warm, and thoughtful tone can enhance communication effectiveness, while a hostile or dismissive tone may obstruct it.
- **Active Listening:** Engaging attentively in conversations by showing interest through nodding, maintaining eye contact, and providing appropriate responses. This entails comprehensively grasping the speaker's message before formulating a reply.
- **Adaptability:** Modifying one's communication approach to fit various audiences and contexts. This requires discernment in determining when to adopt a formal or informal tone, when to employ specialized terminology, and when to simplify the content.
- **Conciseness:** The ability to express in a clear manner only with necessary explanations.
- **Feedback:** The skill to provide and receive feedback in a constructive manner.

3.3 Situational Awareness

Situational awareness is the ability to perceive and understand what is happening around you and anticipate potential risks or changes. In high-risk environments like aviation, healthcare, and maritime operations, this skill is essential for making timely and safe decisions (Endsley, 1995). The sub-criteria of situational awareness skills are listed below, along with their definitions.

- **Environmental Awareness:** Awareness of surroundings such as weather conditions, traffic density, speed, position, UKC (Under Keel Clearance), etc. Recognizing anomalies and unusual changes.
- **Team Awareness:** Understanding the duties, roles, qualifications, and available status of team members and recognizing when a team member needs help or is out of his/her role. Noticing team members' abnormal activities.

- Self-awareness: Recognizing your available fatigue level, perception capacity, emotional state, and body health.
- Foresight: Prediction of the situations in the near future and the effects of these situations.

3.4 Decision making

Decision-making is one of the most important non-technical skills to choose the best way of action among several alternatives based on available information, experience, and judgment. This skill plays a critical role in safety, leadership, and teamwork, especially in high-risk industries like maritime, aviation, and emergency response (Mearns and Flin, 1995). The sub-criteria of decision-making skills are listed below, along with their definitions.

- Problem Definition: Identification of a problem and its causes.
- Risk Assessment and Option Definition: The ability to assess risks and options and choose the best one.
- Creating Options: The ability to produce more than one solution to a problem.
- Outcome Review: Evaluating the potential results.

3.5 Leadership and Managerial Skills

Leadership and managerial skills refer to the ability to guide, motivate, and manage a team effectively. This non-technical help drive team success, enable positive workplace cultures, and ensure organizational goals are met (Hutchinson, 2007). The sub-criteria of leadership and managerial skills are listed below, along with their definitions.

- Delegation: Understanding the appropriate timing and methodologies for the effective allocation of tasks. This practice not only empowers individuals but also fosters team development, concurrently allowing the leader to concentrate on more strategic objectives.
- Planning & Organization: The capability to establish goals, delineate processes, and formulate actionable plans to attain objectives with optimal efficiency. This encompasses the management of time and the allocation of resources.
- Use of authority and self-confidence: The authority of the leader must be judiciously balanced with the confidence and engagement of the team members. Prompt and decisive actions should be undertaken when circumstances require it.
- Inspiration and Motivation: Fostering a constructive and supportive atmosphere while enhancing team morale, particularly during periods of adversity.
- Critical Thinking: The ability to swiftly identify issues and execute effective resolutions. This competency also involves engaging in analytical thinking when confronted with problems.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a systematic list was created by categorizing the criteria for the evaluation of seafarers' non-technical skills. As a result of the literature review, industrial reports, and current practices, five main criteria were identified: teamwork, communication, situational awareness, decision making, leadership, and managerial skills. The list was completed with the sub-criteria created under the main criteria. This list has been made available as a systematic tool for crew recruitment departments of maritime companies, seafarer trainers and assessors, captains, and chief engineers evaluating personnel performance on board.

In the current digital age, where the importance of non-technical skills is increasing day by day, the criteria in the competency assessment list compiled can be improved by weighing their importance in future studies. In addition, these compiled assessment criteria can be adapted and applied to shipboard assessment, simulator-based assessment, and interview-based assessment methods in future studies.

Conflict of Interests

The author declares that for this article, they have no actual, potential, or perceived conflict of interest.

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